

INTERNET INFORMATION AND ITS INTERNATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Annotation: this article is written about the norms of international regulation of the internet and information on it.

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The Internet does not have the status of a legal entity. For this reason, it is not subject to any international organization or specific state. There is no single Center for the distribution of internet resources, including a control center. That is why the materials and information resources used in the use of the internet have the right to private property. At the moment, there are three main groups of subjects on the internet. The creator of the software and the technical part of the information info graph of the network the expansion and development of its operation are the developers of information on the network and programmers who also provide services for connecting to the network. Being consumers of information and network services, in turn, hosting services to information consumers are divided into consumers and consumers of information mail services. Thus, the global internet is a system of developed relationships between different entities with needs and capabilities of different goals. This requires the regulation of their activities and the normative consolidation of their rights and obligations. In the process of managing the internet, many subjects are involved, including the state of civil society business. Since the 1980s, activities have begun to regulate the legal management of the internet in Europe and the United States. To date, there are several stages in the legal management of the internet. International stage, regional stage, national stage. The European Union's standards unify it the European Union is a World Intellectual Property Organization International Chamber of Commerce held international conferences on labor management of the European Economic Commission of the UN. The management of the Global network is enshrined in the Declaration of principles adopted at the Geneva stage of the World Summit on the Legal Information Society, in which public policy related to the internet is defined as the sovereign rights of states. For the last 10 years, the following legal norms have been developed in the rest of the industry. UNISTRA e-commerce act. Electronic signature act. By the European Union, however, the convention on the protection of individuals from automatic processing of personal data the

convention on the protection of individuals from automatic processing of personal data the convention on information and legal cooperation on the services of the additional protocol information society the European Union Convention on cybercrime the basic principles of combining internet regulation. It is indicated in the declaration on free communication on the internet. These cover the following. There are no restrictions on the content of information on the internet self-management of information content on the internet encourages it unprotected it prohibits its groups from using lock filters that interfere with the knowledge of information, in addition to the use of filters that protect access to certain internet sites. Creates the foundations and guarantees of fair trials in disputes. Within the framework of the 1997 International Chamber of Commerce, the general rules for digitally certified international trade and in 1908 the general principles of advertising and marketing on the internet were developed. The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe and the UN Center for trade facilitation and e-business adopted the electronic information exchange agreement for international commercial use in 1995, and the e-commerce agreement in 2000. In the countries of the European Union, the following documents were signed on the legal regulation of the internet. Therefore, in the development of international internet law, it is important to establish countries that are not covered by international legal agreements and to create a basis for their regulation on the basis of the norms of the international legal contract. The contract in the field of internet management the existing conflicts between the norms of law governments are concluded with equal participation of civil society and the private sector. International legal agreements must be resolved through such conditions, the legality of the norms of the relevant international legal agreement is guaranteed, and their implementation will be effective.

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